

Laser polishing of new materials: healing of scratch&dig defects

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Abstract. Scratches and microdefects on glass surfaces significantly impair the optical and mechanical properties of optical components. They already occur during mechanical processing (shaping) and have to be removed in several specific processing steps. A process is presented with which scratches and microdefects can be removed by means of CO₂ laser radiation.

1 State of the art

Conventional mechanical processing of optical surfaces is one of the processes that incur considerable costs and take up a lot of time in the manufacture of optical components. Various grinding, lapping and polishing steps are used to create the geometry and then reduce the surface roughness bit by bit. This is associated with significant material removal, which takes a lot of time, especially in the case of quartz glass, and is accompanied by considerable tool wear. In addition, the mechanical processing in particular leads to deep cracks in the surface (sub surface damages), which have to be removed at great expense in the subsequent steps. [1]

If the surface is then sufficiently well mechanically polished, scratches can quickly appear again, which negatively affect the function of the optical component. In addition, scratches and microdefects are the starting point for the mechanical failure of glass components under load. They significantly lower the mechanical strength. To remove these scratches and microdefects, mechanical polishing would have to be performed again or other expensive polishing processes, such as ion beam polishing or magnetorheological finishing (MRF), would have to be resorted to.

One possibility to remove these scratches and microdefects quickly – and without the use of additional tools and polishing agents – is the laser beam polishing process (LBP). This method has been researched for several years now in numerous scientific studies for different materials. In the field of polishing metallic surfaces, it has already been transferred to industrial production by the development of a special machine technology. [2]. Furthermore, there are numerous publications on investigations into the surface treatment - in particular also polishing - of glass (e.g. [3], [4], [5], [6]).

In [7] and also in [8] the method has already been used to remove scratches from surfaces. In the first example, pulsed laser radiation was applied and scratches could not be completely removed. Furthermore, undesired material upheavals occurred. In the second case, the focus was on a combination of mechanical and laser-assisted processing. Thus, sub surface damages were removed by means of laser beam polishing, and the surface was

subsequently polished again by conventional mechanical means in order to remove unwanted structures resulting from the laser beam polishing.

2 Proceeding

In the present study, it is shown how scratches and microdefects can be smoothed by targeted irradiation of the surface with laser radiation of wavelength 10.6 μm. Laser radiation of this wavelength is almost completely absorbed by quartz glass surfaces and leads to a heating of the surface up to softening. In a flowing process, unevenness or scratches/microdefects are filled and smoothed. This laser polishing process is suitable for polishing a glass surface in a very short time with little effort and without additional tools and polishing agents. On conventionally mechanically polished quartz glass samples of the size 25 x 25 x 3 mm³, diagonally running scratches and microdefects were selectively brought in and the samples were then smoothed using laser radiation. For process monitoring and to prove the effectiveness of the method, the samples were analyzed before the defects were applied afterwards and after laser polishing using confocal sensor (FRT), white light interferometer (WLI) and transmission measurement. The first two methods allow the surface quality to be assessed, while the transmission measurement shows how the scratch changes the optical properties of the material and that this change is eliminated by the treatment with the laser radiation.

3 Experiments and Results

A 2 kW CO₂ laser is used, whose beam is directed by mirrors to a 2D scanning system and from this system into the polishing chamber. The beam diameter of the parallel beam used is 7.1 mm and in order to achieve a uniform energy input, this beam is deflected linearly at high speed (1400 mm/s). The resulting polishing line is guided over the specimen surface in an additional y-movement with a speed of 34 mm/min. The overlap of the lines is over 90%, so a homogeneous energy input can therefore be assumed, which prevents the formation of a "polishing structure".

From previous investigations it is known that a certain energy input is required to heat the surface of amorphous SiO₂ to the point where flow occurs. The calculated energy input resulting from the machining parameters is 500 J/mm², which leads to an average sample heating of about 2100°C. The temperature is thus within the previously determined range of 1900 to 2100 °C for successful laser polishing without significant material removal. This temperature is determined by means of a thermal imaging camera, which is used for process monitoring. To avoid new defects on the glass surface during the removal of the scratches and microdefects, it must be cleaned very well before polishing and the polishing environment should contain as few particles (dust) as possible. Residues on the surface and dust from the environment have been shown to cause defects on laser-treated surfaces [9]. Therefore, laser polishing always takes place in a polishing chamber in which filters are applied to ensure a reduction of particles in the surrounding air. During the polishing process, the high thermal shock resistance of quartz glass means that additional heating of the specimens is not necessary, which is not possible with other glass materials. After irradiation of the specimens, however, they are then treated in a heating furnace to remove introduced stresses that would negatively affect the mechanical durability of the fused quartz elements and their optical properties (optical path difference).

The mechanically polished samples have a surface roughness of Sq = 18 nm. After removal of the scratch, this value was even reduced to Sq = 10 nm. The scratches (a section of one can be seen in Fig. 1) have an average depth of approximately 5.1 µm, are about 100 µm wide and there are partially occurring material upheavals in the range of 1 µm. The roughness measured inside the scratch is Rq = 3.1 µm. This is within the range defined as suitable for LBP in previous investigations [9].

By treating the surfaces with the laser radiation, the scratch and the microdefects can be reduced and after parameter optimization – finally – removed. Fig. 2 shows the part of a scratch that has not been completely removed. The flowing of the material has not been sufficient to completely smooth out the defect. Tiny dimples remain. It could also be observed that if the scratches are not completely leveled, a uniform deepening (depth about approx. 0.7 µm) remains. In other words, this means that the surface does not show any clearly defined defects, the roughness remains the same (in relation to the surrounding area) but the shape of the surface is changed.

Fig. 1. Detail of a scratch on a mechanically polished surface.

Fig. 2. Scratch, not completely removed (detail).

Table 1 shows some of the surface characteristics of the fused silica samples during the investigations. These are measured values from the measurements on the WLI and on the FRT. Although the measuring conditions (measuring field size, filter settings, etc.) were selected the same, the measured values differ. This can be explained by the different measuring methods.

Table 1. Surface parameters before and after laser polishing.

Sample...	WLI [nm]		FRT [nm]	
	Sq	Rq	Sq	Rq
mechanically polished	13	15	18	14
LBP incl./on scratch residue	27	15	16	27
residue-free LBP	12	12	10	12

Another way to check the quality of optical elements is to measure their transmission. A quartz glass component with perfect, scratch- and defect-free surfaces transmits a certain amount of light during the transmission measurement. However, if there are defects on the surfaces, there is a loss of transmission due to absorption or diffusion. This fact can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of LBP as well. A goniospectrophotometer is applied to determine the influence of the scratches and microdefects on the transmitted light. Because the introduced surface defects account for only about 0.6 % of the total surface area, the change in the detected light

amounts to only a few percent as well. The scratches and microdefects reduce the measured value by 2.1 % after LBP, the difference is 1.4 % (to the untreated, mechanically polished sample). Thus, even if scratches and microdefects can no longer be detected by FRT or WLI, there are losses. Where they come from must be investigated further.

4 Conclusion

The results of the presented study show that it is possible to completely remove scratches and microdefects from fused silica surfaces using laser beam polishing. Future investigations will continue to search for suitable methods to control the results better and faster. The measurements at the FRT take a lot of time (30 min/mm²), the WLI reaches its limits (with the polished surfaces) due to its measuring principle and the transmission measurement seems to be too less significant in the form used so far. It is also necessary to determine in future experiments how scratches and microdefects can be characterized in preparation of machining on the basis of their lateral and vertical expansions, so that they can then be specifically eliminated. Indeed, the investigations also show that too much introduced energy leads to a deformation of the entire sample.

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